

Current Status of Vietnamese Law on Procedures and Processes for Mediation of Individual Labor Disputes by Labor Mediators

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Abstract: In today's increasingly dynamic and integrated Vietnamese labor market, conflicts of interest between workers and employers are inevitable and have shown signs of increasing in number. To address these disputes, Vietnamese law has established a strict procedure and process. The initial stage of resolving labor disputes is the mediation process conducted by labor mediators, who act as a bridge to help the disputing parties find common ground and reach an agreement. The frequency of labor disputes, especially between individual workers and employers, has increased significantly in recent years. The Covid-19 pandemic has exacerbated this issue. This article analyzes the limitations of the current legal framework governing mediation in labor disputes and draws on international best practices to propose recommendations for improvement. The goal is to enhance the legal framework for resolving labor disputes and meet the evolving needs of the labor market.

Keywords: Dispute, Individual Labor Dispute, Mediation, Labor Mediator

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1. To State the Problem

When establishing a labor relationship, both the worker and the employer must agree on the job, wages, working hours, and other working conditions. This agreement serves as the basis for both parties to exercise their rights and fulfill their obligations, and the result of this process is a labor contract. Although labor contracts are essentially entered into on a voluntary and mutually agreed-upon basis, aiming to establish a legal foundation to enhance the sense of responsibility of both parties in the contract's performance, entering into a contract and performing a contract are two entirely different matters. During the performance, certain reasons may lead to conflicting interests between the parties, resulting in disputes. If these disputes are not resolved promptly, they can adversely affect economic life, political security, social order, and safety, and especially impact the worker and their family (Ho Chi Minh City University of Law, 2022).

In terms of terminology, labor disputes were previously understood as "conflicts" between workers and employers. This understanding was maintained for quite a long time in Vietnam and acknowledged conflicts as an issue of labor relations. In the South during the Republic of Vietnam regime, the term "labor disputes" was used to refer to this content. From an academic perspective, according to views recorded in research works, "labor disputes are disagreements in the application of labor law, collective agreements, local regulations, labor

contracts, or related to the establishment or change of existing working conditions that have not been resolved through direct negotiations between workers and employers" (S.M. Bortnyk, K.Iu. Melnyk, L.V. Mohilevskyi, 2019). Mediation in individual labor disputes can be understood as a process where the disputing parties, unable to negotiate a settlement on their own, seek the assistance of a neutral third party - a labor mediator - to facilitate the resolution of the dispute and help the parties find common ground (Kyselova O.I. & Myrhorod-Karpova V.V., 2022).

Vietnam's labor law has, to date, established a relatively tight system of procedures for resolving labor disputes, which has become increasingly effective in handling disputes. Labor mediation is the first method in the process of resolving a labor dispute. Accordingly, the parties will sit down to negotiate, present their conflicting issues, and together consider finding a common solution under the guidance and influence of the mediator so that legal rights and interests are balanced based on respect for the will and self-determination of the parties. Therefore, mediation, as a method for resolving disputes arising in areas such as civil, commercial, and labor, is considered a promising dispute resolution method in law enforcement, especially in the non-judicial aspect and has the potential to be applied in marriage and family, labor, and other types of disputes (Zapara S. I., Vyhlyazova M. V., Kolomiiets I. S., 2016).

Globally, and especially in Western countries, mediation has long been considered a positive and effective method for resolving labor disputes, even in some advanced countries, when labor disputes arise, parties prefer mediation to judicial methods such as arbitration or litigation (Fjolla Kaprolli Ismaili, 2021). Labor mediation has been stipulated in a number of International Labour Organization (ILO) instruments such as Recommendation No. 92 (of 29 June 1951 concerning the voluntary adjustment of disputes); Convention No. 154 (of 19 June 1981 concerning the promotion of collective bargaining)... In Vietnamese law, labor dispute mediation is regulated in the Labor Codes over the years and implementing guidelines. Labor dispute mediation is an effective method to bring workers and employers closer together, bypassing barriers of social status, legal awareness, and unequal positions in the relationship.

Although mediation is an effective method for resolving disputes, in recent years, the activities of labor dispute mediation in general and individual labor dispute mediation in particular have still faced many difficulties due to legal barriers. The legal framework related to the resolution of individual labor disputes is still inadequate, and some provisions are unclear, leading to confusion among competent agencies and organizations in resolving disputes, thus, the legitimate interests of workers in some cases have not been fully guaranteed (Tran Thi Nha Nhung, 2022). To contribute to the maximum protection of the rights of the parties in labor disputes, it is necessary to study and improve the legal framework for the method of resolving labor disputes between individual workers and employers, thereby creating a premise for labor dispute resolution through mediation to become more effective and ensure timeliness, efficiency, and flexibility in the future.

2. The legal framework for individual labor dispute mediation by labor mediators in Vietnam

2.1. Regarding the time limit for the procedures to resolve disputes through mediation by a mediator

Pursuant to Clause 1, Article 188 of the Labor Code 2019, individual labor disputes must be settled through the mediation procedure of a labor mediator before

requesting the Labor Arbitration Council or the Court to settle, except for labor disputes that are not required to go through the mediation procedure. Clause 2, Article 188 of the Labor Code 2019 stipulates: "The labor mediator must complete the mediation within 05 working days from the date of receipt of the request from the party requesting dispute resolution; In cases where the labor specialized agency of the People's Committee receives a request for labor dispute resolution, it has the responsibility to transfer the request to the labor mediator within 05 working days for cases that are required to go through the labor mediation procedure". In cases where the labor mediator directly receives a petition from the party requesting dispute resolution, within 12 hours from the time of receipt of the petition, the mediator must transfer it to the Department of Labor, Invalids and Social Affairs or the Labor, Invalids and Social Affairs Division that is managing the labor mediator for classification and processing of the petition. Within the next 12 hours from the time of receiving the petition from the labor mediator, the above-mentioned labor specialized agencies must issue a document appointing the labor mediator in accordance with Clause 2, Article 95 of Decree 145/2020/ND-CP. Accordingly, within a maximum of 24 consecutive hours (1 day) from the time the labor mediator receives the petition from the party requesting dispute resolution, the labor mediator can have the full authority to conduct mediation, as evidenced by the document appointing the labor mediator of the labor specialized agency that is managing the mediator. Through the above provisions, the author finds some difficulties as follows:

Firstly, the provision of an identical deadline for mediators to conduct conciliation in both cases of receiving an application is unreasonable. This is because, in the case where the disputing parties submit an application to a specialized labor agency, the time limit for conducting the conciliation procedure is not calculated from the date of receipt of the application. Instead, these agencies have 5 days to classify and process the application before forwarding it to the labor mediator. Only then does the time limit for conducting conciliation begin to be counted from the date the mediator receives the request from the aforementioned specialized agency, and the conciliation must be completed within the following 5 days. However, in the case where the labor mediator directly receives a request from the party seeking to resolve the dispute, the time limit for settlement is calculated from the date the mediator receives this request. Within 12 hours of receipt, the mediator must forward the application to the specialized agency that manages them for classification and processing, before issuing a written notification appointing a mediator to resolve the dispute. Accordingly, in this case, the specialized agencies only have 12 hours to classify and process the application, and the mediator only has 4 full days to conduct the conciliation. It can be seen that, while ensuring the speed and timeliness of dispute resolution through conciliation, in order for this activity to achieve maximum effectiveness, there needs to be a suitable timeframe for individuals and relevant agencies to effectively fulfill their roles, contributing to the fair and equitable resolution of disputes regarding the rights and interests of the parties.

Secondly, the law is still unclear about the time limit for completing procedures prior to conciliation, leading to unforeseen situations. Decree 145/2020/ND-CP stipulates that the mediator has "12 hours" to transfer the request to the specialized agency, and the specialized agency processes the application and issues a written notification appointing a mediator within "12 hours," but it does not clarify whether the 12 hours in this case refers to working hours or 12 consecutive hours, including non-working hours. Accordingly, it is unclear how to handle cases where applications are received on working days preceding a weekend or holiday, while in cases where the requesting party submits the application directly to the specialized agency, the law clearly states the processing time as "5 working days".

Thirdly, according to Clause 3, Article 181 of the 2019 Labor Code, the specialized labor agency under the People's Committee is the focal point for receiving labor dispute resolution requests and is responsible for classifying, guiding, supporting, and assisting the parties in resolving disputes. In other words, when a person requesting dispute resolution submits an application to the specialized labor agency under the People's Committee, this agency will receive and process the dispute resolution request, guide and support the parties before sending it to the labor mediator, creating conditions for the parties to understand the process and their rights, and facilitating the conciliation process. However, the author argues that the responsibility of the People's Committee when receiving dispute resolution requests is still unclear. The law vaguely stipulates the responsibilities of the focal agencies receiving requests but does not specify the criteria for support and assistance. In what cases should assistance be provided to balance the interests of the parties in dispute resolution? At the same time, there are no sanctions to be applied in cases where individuals or relevant agencies responsible fail to perform or perform inadequately or incompletely their responsibilities, or commit violations in the process of resolving disputes between the parties.

Through the analysis, it can be seen that there is a need for a change in the legal basis to overcome the above-mentioned obstacles, specifically:

Amend the regulations on the timeframe for receiving, classifying, and processing dispute resolution requests by the focal agency – the Specialized Labor Agency under the People's Committee to standardize the processing procedures in both cases of application receipt. The specialized agency should be given more time to process requests and propose support measures to guide the parties in resolving disputes most effectively. Additionally, clearly and uniformly stipulate the time limit for dispute resolution in each stage as "working hours," and also provide for the handling of cases where applications are submitted at the end of the day or on days preceding weekends, holidays, or Tet. Finally, detailed regulations should be developed outlining the specific criteria for the support and assistance that specialized labor agencies are required to provide to disputing parties, thereby enhancing the feasibility of this provision. Concurrently, penalties should be established to address violations and negligence in receiving, processing, and resolving conciliation requests by relevant individuals and agencies. This aims to impose legal consequences on those with authority and responsibility who commit violations, thereby increasing the sense of responsibility among labor mediators and specialized labor management agencies.

2.2. Regarding the settlement of disputes that do not require prior mediation

Clause 1, Article 188 of the 2019 Labor Code mandates a mediation procedure conducted by a labor mediator for labor disputes between individual employees and employers, except in the following cases: i) Disciplinary sanctions of dismissal or unilateral termination of the labor contract; ii) Compensation for damages and severance pay upon termination of the labor contract; iii) Disputes between domestic workers and employers; iv) Disputes related to social insurance, health insurance, unemployment insurance, occupational accidents and occupational diseases insurance; Disputes concerning compensation for damages between employees and enterprises or organizations sending employees to work abroad under contract; and disputes between leased employees and leased employers. Besides, Clause 7, Article 188 of the 2019 Labor Code also stipulates that in cases where mediation is not mandatory, the parties have the right to choose one of the two remaining dispute resolution methods: requesting a labor arbitration council or a court. Accordingly, when there is a request for labor dispute resolution, the specialized agency for labor matters under

the People's Committee shall be the focal point for receiving, processing, classifying, and transferring to the competent individual or organization for settlement within 05 working days. Disputes that are required to go through the mediation procedure shall be transferred to the labor mediator, while disputes that fall under the case of requesting the Arbitration Council for settlement shall be transferred to the Arbitration Council, or guided to the Court for settlement in accordance with Clause 3, Article 181 of the 2019 Labor Code. Disputes that fall under the case of requesting the Arbitration Council for settlement include: i) Disputes that are not mandatory to go through the mediation procedure; ii) The mediation period has expired but the labor mediator has not conducted mediation; iii) Mediation has failed.

Accordingly, it can be understood that in cases where mediation is not mandatory, the parties may or may not choose mediation. However, the law only stipulates that mediation is not mandatory in these cases and does not specify which subject has the right to request mediation proceedings in cases where the parties wish to resolve the dispute through mediation, as the law allows for the choice of mediation or not, but does not completely exclude the mediation procedure. It should be noted that the meaning of "not mandatory to go through the mediation procedure" does not mean "not to conduct mediation", in this case the parties still have the right to request mediation but according to the above provisions, the mediation procedure has been excluded from the dispute resolution process of the parties. Thus, it can be seen that the above provisions are contradictory when they both stipulate that the parties may or may not mediate in cases where mediation is not mandatory, and also exclude the parties' right to choose the method of mediation, forcing the parties to choose one of the two remaining settlement methods.

To address this issue, it is necessary to supplement provisions to clearly guide the parties' right to request mediation and the procedure for exercising this right in cases where mediation is not mandatory under Clause 1, Article 188. In addition, Clause 7, Article 188 should be amended as follows: "In cases where mediation is not mandatory under Clause 1, Article 188 and the parties do not request mediation,..." they shall have the right to choose one of the two remaining settlement methods. This opens up the option for parties to choose the simplest and shortest dispute resolution path when faced with a choice of settlement methods, and only resort to judicial methods when they cannot reach a consensus. This change is in line with the principle of prioritizing the settlement of labor disputes through mediation on the basis of respecting the rights and interests of both disputing parties, respecting the common interests of society, and not violating the law. It creates maximum conditions for the parties to resolve disputes peacefully and promptly through mediation.

2.3. Authority to attend a mediation hearing

According to Clause 3, Article 188 of the 2019 Labor Code, both disputing parties must be present at the mediation session. The disputing parties may authorize another person to participate in the mediation session. On the other hand, according to point a, Clause 1, Article 179 of the 2019 Labor Code, individual labor disputes are disputes between an employee and an employer; between an employee and an enterprise or organization sending employees to work abroad under contract; and between a leased employee and a leased employer. The purpose of mediation is to provide the parties to the dispute with a favorable opportunity to agree on their lawful rights and interests. In other words, when one party submits a request for dispute resolution, the other party is the competent authority to resolve the claims regarding rights and interests. However, according to the above provisions, the parties are allowed to

authorize a third party to participate in the mediation session. The author argues that this provision is unreasonable, specifically as follows:

Firstly, in mediation sessions, mediators act as intermediaries, facilitating reconciliation between the parties, providing them with an opportunity to listen to each other's difficulties and aspirations, which is the basis for reaching a mutual agreement. By authorizing a third party to participate in the session, the parties do not directly express their own wishes and intentions, nor do they have the opportunity to address the difficulties and obstacles that are the root cause of a labor dispute. Consequently, the mediator cannot effectively fulfill their role in balancing the rights and obligations of the parties. In other words, it is difficult to build a good-faith relationship through third-party representation in dispute resolution sessions, making it challenging to achieve a successful mediation. This is consistent with the provisions on the principles of conducting labor mediation procedures by mediators as regulated in Ukraine's Mediation Law of November 16, 2021.

Secondly, the parties involved in mediation, under the guidance of the labor mediator, must express their wishes and intentions, and present their views on the other party's demands. On the part of the employee, the authorized representative must clearly understand the difficulties and issues that need to be resolved by the employer, and must also grasp the necessary issues related to the employment relationship between the employer and the employee, such as the employment contract, wages, and other benefits that the employee actually receives, in order to provide information to the labor mediator as a basis for resolving the dispute. On the employer's side, in addition to issues directly related to the employee involved in the dispute, the authorized representative, within the scope of dispute resolution, must be well-versed in issues related to the employer, such as wage and bonus regulations, employee welfare policies, and the economic situation (if any), to effectively participate in the dispute resolution process at the mediation session. Accordingly, the author argues that it is necessary to have specific regulations on the qualifications of authorized representatives participating in mediation sessions - this is the basis to ensure the effectiveness of labor mediation sessions and to enhance the role of mediators in working with the parties to resolve disputes.

Thirdly, regarding the authorization to participate in mediation sessions, the scope of authority of the authorized representative is crucial. This is because, when conducting labor mediation, the success of the mediation session and the achievement of a settlement primarily rely on the principles of equality, freedom, and mutual agreement under the guidance of the mediator. Thus, to resolve disputes in the mediation stage, both parties must be subjects capable of fulfilling their rights and interests within the scope of the other party's demands, and have the right to negotiate on the disputes between the parties during the dispute resolution process. Therefore, the author believes that when authorizing another subject to participate in the mediation session, the authorized representative must have certain powers within the scope of their authorization, such as the power to decide to accept the demands of the other parties or to adjust the demands of the authorizing party to resolve the dispute in the case.

2.4. The disputing parties were absent from the mediation session

According to Clause 1, Article 188 of the 2019 Labor Code, except in cases where mediation is not mandatory, individual labor disputes must be mediated before being referred to a Labor Arbitration Council or a Court. This is a prerequisite for the parties involved in the

dispute to have the opportunity to negotiate and voluntarily resolve their differences with the support and guidance of a labor mediator in a spirit of goodwill, equality, and mutual agreement. To ensure the prompt and timely resolution of disputes, the law stipulates that within 5 working days from the date of "receiving the request from the party requesting dispute resolution" or "from the labor specialized agency of the People's Committee," the mediator must conclude the mediation. In comparison with the provisions of Clause 4, Article 188 of the 2019 Labor Code, which specifically states: "In the event that the mediation plan is not accepted or if a disputing party has been duly summoned for the second time but is still absent without a valid reason, the labor mediator shall draw up a record of unsuccessful mediation. The record of unsuccessful mediation must be signed by the disputing party who is present and the labor mediator". As per the aforementioned regulations, if the disputing parties are absent from two consecutive summons without a valid reason, the mediator shall terminate the mediation process by issuing a certificate of unsuccessful mediation. With the certificate of unsuccessful mediation, the parties have the basis to request the Labor Arbitration Council or the Court to settle their dispute. From a broader perspective of civil dispute resolution methods, this is a completely reasonable approach, as when one of the parties deliberately refuses to participate in mediation, it demonstrates a lack of goodwill and unwillingness to negotiate to find a mutual solution, thus necessitating the use of judicial methods to resolve the dispute. However, considering labor disputes in particular, this approach currently faces challenges and does not fully guarantee the rights of the parties in certain cases.

Firstly, the law does not specifically stipulate the time at which the mediator must send a summons to the disputing parties to participate in the mediation session. The law's omission of specific procedures for conducting mediation leads to inconsistency in resolving disputes through this method. For example, in complex disputes, mediators may exploit this loophole to avoid conducting mediation. Thus, if the mediation period expires without the mediator taking any action, the dispute will be referred to the Labor Arbitration Council or the Court. In relation to this issue, some European countries have specific regulations regarding the mediator's obligation to organize a mediation session after receiving a mediation request. For example, the Republic of Macedonia stipulates in Clause 1, Article 21 of the Law on Peaceful Resolution of Labor Disputes: "The mediator has the obligation to arrange a hearing within three days of receiving the proposal and documents related to the dispute and to notify the parties thereof". This enhances the effectiveness of mediation and concretizes the mediation process that labor mediators must follow upon receiving a case.

Secondly, the law allows parties to be absent from a mediation session if they have a valid reason. However, it does not exclude the possibility that the parties' absence for a valid reason could prolong the mediation period. Accordingly, the mediation period is limited to 5 working days in all cases, including cases where the parties wish to mediate but are absent due to objective reasons. Therefore, if the mediation period expires and the absent party has not yet remedied the so-called "valid reason," the mediator is also forced to terminate the mediation. In addition, the law does not clarify whether, if a party is absent for a valid reason a second time, the mediator will then summon them for a subsequent session. Currently, there is no specific guidance for handling this situation. The aforementioned shortcomings make it difficult to resolve disputes through mediation, which may lead the parties to resort to judicial methods of resolution, exacerbating conflicts between employees and employers and thereby reducing the effectiveness of labor dispute resolution.

To address the above shortcomings, it is suggested that the regulations on the mediation period be amended as follows: "The labor mediator must conclude the mediation within 5 working days from the date of receipt of the request from the party requesting dispute resolution or from the authority as prescribed in Clause 3, Article 181 of this Law. In case of objective obstacles or the absence of parties for a valid reason, the time limit may be extended but not to exceed 10 working days". This increases the flexibility of dispute resolution through mediation in cases where there are valid reasons or objective obstacles that prevent mediation from being completed within 5 working days. At the same time, it still ensures the timeliness and efficiency in resolving disputes and harmonizing labor relations between individuals and employers.

In addition, it is necessary to supplement specific and detailed regulations on the procedures for conducting mediation by specifying the time when the mediator must send a written summons to the parties to participate in the mediation session. In cases where the parties do not participate or are absent for a valid reason, specific handling procedures need to be prescribed. This avoids the shifting of responsibilities among the entities with authority to resolve disputes. It creates a synchronized legal basis for effectively resolving labor disputes at the mediation stage nationwide.

3. Conclusion

Mediation is a highly effective and practical method of dispute resolution that aligns with the will of all disputing parties. It is encouraged for application in most types of disputes, helping parties achieve their desired rights and interests peacefully, rather than through unilateral decisions of competent authorities in other dispute resolution methods that are prone to errors and lack of objectivity in their judgments, leading to difficulties in practical enforcement of dispute resolution decisions. Therefore, in the world today, there is a view that resolution by mandatory decisions has become less effective compared to the development of the socio-economic context (Iaresko A, 1998).

The establishment of a comprehensive legal framework for dispute resolution through mediation plays an important role in regulating the relationship between employers and employees, promoting the development of an effective solution for labor dispute resolution in line with the general development trends of many countries in the world. However, the current law on labor dispute mediation is still incomplete, with many shortcomings and inconsistencies, affecting the effectiveness of this method.

The consequences of the Covid-19 pandemic on the economy have not yet been fully overcome, coupled with the impact of the war in the Middle East, which has indirectly had a negative impact on labor relations in society in general and individual workers in particular. Improving the effectiveness of the application of mediation in resolving disputes needs to be prioritized and become urgent to promptly resolve arising labor disputes. Moreover, resolving disputes through mediation helps the parties to maintain the opportunity to cooperate with each other after the dispute, helping workers keep their jobs and employers retain their workforce, maintaining the stability and efficiency of production and business operations. A solid legal framework contributes to increasing the success rate of mediation in disputes, thereby helping to balance the interests of the parties, helping businesses and employers avoid reputational damage when having to participate in litigation to compete for rights with their employees.

Through this article, the author proposes suggestive solutions for amending the legal system to align with the development trends of society and address current shortcomings. This lays the foundation for building a most complete dispute resolution mechanism, resolving labor disputes quickly and effectively, especially disputes between individual workers and employers. It aims to build a peaceful and united society and, more deeply, contribute to the development of the economy and social security.

4. References

1. Labor Code 2019;
2. The Law on Peaceful Resolution of Labor Disputes of the Republic of Macedonia;
3. Law on Mediation of Ukraine of 16.11.2021 No 1875–IX;
4. Government Decree No. 145/2020/ND-CP of December 14, 2020, which provides detailed regulations for implementing certain provisions of the Labor Code related to working conditions and labor relations;
5. Ho Chi Minh City University of Law, 2022. Labor Law Textbook, Hong Duc Publishing House;
6. Fjolla Kaprolli Ismaili. 2021. Mediation in solving labor disputes, International Journal Vol.49.5, page-1062;
7. Iaresko A, 1998. Expediency of functioning of commissions on labor disputes. Law of Ukraine. No 4. P. 66;
8. Kyselova O.I & Myrhorod-Karpova V.V., 2022. Mediation in labor disputes, Scientific notes of the Lviv University of Business and Law. The series is economical. Legal series. Issue 32/2022;
9. S.M. Bortnyk, K.Iu. Melnyk, L.V. Mohilevskyi and others, 2019. Labor law of Ukraine: textbook / Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine, Kharkiv National University of Internal Affairs, Kharkiv. P. 408;
10. http://w1.c1.rada.gov.ua/pls/zweb2/webproc4_1?pf3511=68877 (retrieved 24.11.2021);
11. Tran Thi Nha Nhung. 2022. Individual Labor Disputes: Practices and Solutions to Limitations, Vietnam Bar Association Journal, <https://svn.vn/tranh-chap-lao-dong-ca-nhan-thuc-tien-va-giai-phap-han-che1661868568.html>;
12. Zapara S. I., Vyhlazova M. V., Kolomiets I. S., 2016. Establishment of the institute of mediation in Ukraine: Journal of Kyiv University of Law. Kyiv. No 4. P. 125-129.